

SOCIAL CHANGE AND SHARI'AH LEGAL SYSTEM: A PARADIGM FOR PEACE AND CONFLICT RESOLUTION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The view that Nigeria was engulfed by series of conflicts needs no denial. Despite the fact that these conflicts are multi-factorial in nature, they were always been offered religious interpretations for selfish reasons better known to the concerned predators. The fact is, most at time, the people involved in this type of crises whether religious or otherwise, are not lacking the necessary wherewithal in understanding the consequences of such crises. But the reality is, they lacked the concept of God-fearing. It is Taqwa (God fearing) that will lead an individual to imbibe the culture of honesty, humility, kindness, love and affection, generosity and sincerity. This paper therefore argued that the Shari'ah legal system will inevitably play an important role in curbing not only religious crisis but all other kinds of crises like insurgency, banditry, kidnapping and brigandage among others. It will also be an important tool towards reconciling the differences between different ethnic groups and faiths.

Keywords: Shari'ah, Nigeria, Conflict, Peace, Resolution, Taqwa,

Introduction

There were far-flung historical as well as sociological works that hugely elaborated the magnanimity of religion on societal morality and belief. ¹ Social change constitutes selected modifications or replacements in social process, structure, values, customs and way of conducting oneself. It is believed that in every

society twofold divisions of the world exist; the profane and the sacred. Religion is therefore defined to be the belief and practices connected tightly to the sacred which inevitably unite into single moral community (Onwuefeogwu,2009:225). However, there is a cross section of scholars who maintained divergent opinions on the unitary operation of religion. The exponents of this conflicting idea suggest

that religion too, does not always bind a group of people, but in so many instances is the cause of disunity (ibid).

By nature, a significant percentage of people always want to indulge in perpetrating flagrant crimes such as, extortion, brigandage, unnecessary killings, kidnapping, arsons and political assassinations. The most unfortunate thing is that these crimes, on so many occasions are being carried out under the disguise of religion. On the contrary, however, Islam is trying to put an end to all these and establish a spiritual and religious purpose for even human instincts and desires. It is in relation to this that Islam as a religion, placed so many restrictions on human activities and thoughts with a view to bringing them under divine control. In the context of this paper, the concept of morality has been singled out as an aspect of social change in the society. The intent of this paper is to shed light on the role of Shari'ah legal system on social change in Nigeria. The paper therefore is of the view that, if the divine laws are put into practice, the level of religious crises and other unnecessary killings would reduce to a minimal level which will in turn lead to strict adherence to the concept of social order in Nigeria.

Conceptualizing Morality.

According to Advanced Learners' Dictionary, 'morality' is the recognition

of the distinction between good and evil or between right and wrong. In other words, it is the respect for and obedience to the rule of right conduct. However, Fagothey, (1976:2) in his contribution to the concept of morality, he conceptualized it; as the study of right and wrong, of good and evil in human conduct. It can be correctly deduced from the definitions presented that an individual is to be properly oriented on how to become an acceptable member of his society. Morality, is therefore remained the only giant machine that could be used to achieve the desired objective, which is the violent-free society.

Historically, societies of different ages and spaces possessed and passed different norms and values through which an individual is to be judged. In fact, moral behavior, which is the by-product of attitudinal change, teaches people how to become acceptable members of their society. To sum it up, moral uprightness is the overwhelming surrender and obedience to the code of conduct generally known as norms and values in contradiction from societal taboo (Abubakar, 2010:128).

Islamic Shari'ah Legal System versus Morality

From the Shari'ah legal system view point, morality is generally

perceived as the firm belief in Allah the supreme as well as the exhibition of good behavior in all ramifications (Gada, 2010:128). With this therefore, morality is multi-dimensional for the fact that it covers all facets of human life. Interestingly, some of the significant features of Islam which is the main source of Shari'ah legal system are its moral, ethical and humanitarian aspects (ibid). All these in Islam are generally based on equality between the people, brotherhood, justice and hard work for the cause of the society (ibid).

The basic objective of Islam as a complete and comprehensive way of life as enshrined in the Quran and other Islamic sources is humanistic, ethical, moral, spiritual and religious concern.² All these aforementioned areas of concern are explicitly explained in the glorious Quran and the traditions or sayings of the Prophet (S.A.W.). The Quran (23:8) made reference;

“Those who are faithfully true to their *Amanat* (all the duties which Allah has ordained, honesty, moral responsibility and trust) and to their covenants”

The above Qur'anic injunction, clearly describes people who are honest, adhered to their moral responsibility and are trustworthy in all their dealings with

their fellow human beings. One of the objectives of Islamic education is that the freedom of man is his endowment with intellect to distinguish rights from wrong, vices from virtues among other things (Ibrahim, 2014:113).

The lack of endurance and commitment to the spirit of brotherhood is one of the characteristics of the contemporary existing society. And the reality is, a society that lacked the culture of endurance and spirit of brotherhood will inevitably wallow in different sorts of criminality. Little wonder therefore, Islam strongly enjoined the believers to perpetually exhibit the culture of optimum endurance and brotherhood, and to dwell much in doing the righteous deeds. Qur'an (103:1-3) states that:

By the time, verily man is in loss, except those who believe and do righteous good deeds, and recommend one another to the truth and recommend one another to patience.

The above chapter clearly indicated that man as Allah's vicegerent on earth has two fundamental tasks as far as societal development is concerned. The first is to integrate the conduct of righteous deeds in his entire life. The essence of this hinges on the absolute soul purification that will lead him in keeping away from perpetrating crimes. Secondly, the shari'a legal system or

Islam generally made it mandatory upon all believers to recommend or exhort their fellow human beings to the conduct of righteous deeds. The philosophy behind this clarion call is that society may find it very easy in having violent-free society if they share common moral characteristics and ethical values.³ The objective of Islam here is to create love, fraternity and brotherhood. In essence, a society that is morally sound devoid of any form of hatred.

The above Qur'anic interpretation was further supported by the tradition of the Prophet (P.B.U.H), where he categorically stated: "None of you is a true believer until he loves for his brother, what he loves for himself".

In a precise language, the *hadith* is teaching the generality of the Muslim community the spirit of love, brotherhood and fraternity.

The magnanimity of morality and other ethical conducts could be deduced from these huge lessons that prophet Luqman taught his little son. Luqman *Al-Hikmah* admonished his son to keep away from polytheism, arrogance, pride and all sort of insolence. The Qur'an (31:17), says:

O my son! Perform *As-salat* (prayer), enjoin people all that is good, and forbid People all that is evil and bad, and bear with patience

whatever befalls you. Verily, these are some of the important commandments ordained by Allah.

The above verse emphasizes on the importance of positive moral upbringing through the inculcation of positive moral values in the individual. In particular, prophet Luqman taught his son to treat his fellow human beings with kindness, humility and respect. He also urged him to caution people about things that are evil and advise people on all that is good. Another important lesson that Luqman taught his son, is patience. The wisdom behind patience is, all the aforementioned commandments will not be achieved in the absence of patience.

Essentially, whatever the circumstances, the central position of Islam and Shari'ah is changing the society from wrong to right or from bad to good. This position is known in Islam as '*amr bi al-ma'ruf wa al-nahy an al-munkar*' (commanding the right and forbidding the wrong). This is also the general meaning of Shari'a (Bugaje, 2015:50-51). In line with this, Islam enjoins the society to imbibe the culture of love and affection, honesty and sincerity, tolerance, forgiveness and humility. By implication, a person that internalizes these characteristics is ultimately a person of decent character. Therefore, in its general sense, the concept of morality in all contexts,

embraces fear of Allah, justice, honesty, generosity, and kindness among others. And the moment these aforementioned characteristics are achieved, the society will inevitably change.

Role of Shari'ah Legal System in Social Change

It is beyond denial that the contemporary situation in Nigeria is characterized by so many misfortunes and calamities. Religious crises, political assassination, kidnapping, brigandage, arson and insurgency remain the order of the day. All these different categories of crimes are being perpetrated through religious bigotry, tribal sentiment and lack of fear of God. The need therefore for the divine laws in this disgusting condition is very critical. There is no doubt that regional conflicts and long-standing tribal conflict not only in Nigeria but among the Arabs during the barbaric period over scarce natural resources hindered the absorption of the values of solidarity and met tribal thinking that underlie Islamic social institutions such as the family, citizenship, and the concepts of state and nation (Abusulayman, 2013:3). With this therefore, taking a cursory look into the general objective of *Shari'ah*, it certainly has a gigantic role to play. Ibn Ashur, (1968;10-15), in his work titled 'the treatise on *Maqasid ai-Shariah* aptly

summed up the general objectives of Islamic legislation in the following words:

The shari'ah's general rules and specific proofs indicate that the all-purpose principle of Islamic legislation is to preserve the social order of communities and insure their health. Explicit textual proofs confirm that the overall objective of the shari'ah is to remove corruption in all kinds of human activity... the concept of *maslahah* means utmost righteousness and goodness and an attribute of the act whereby righteousness takes place in public or private. It is also useful or beneficial for the public or individuals.

A careful examination of the above *maqasid al-shari'ah (intent)* and its link with the concept of social change or order, reveal the true meaning of rightly guided freedom exercised in a spirit of fairness, dignity, justice and tolerance. In essence, adequate application of the general objective of Shari'ah protects the community from the evils of tyranny, authoritarianism, injustice, corruption and general intolerance.

As discussed in the paper, one of the most central pillars or objectives of Islam generally, is to instill the fear of Allah in the mind of the individual. The

fact is, the fear of Allah has huge influence on the physiological and sociological human responses. This will therefore instill so the much-desired characteristics needed in the process of social change. Some of these characteristics include; honesty, hard work, transparency, love and affection, generosity, humility, justice and sincerity. Little wonder Arnold (1968:10-15) concluded that:

To promote a better example showing how moral and ethical quality helped in its spread, it is important to reflect on the moral code followed by the founder of Islam and then by his immediate successors for they were the true incarnation of Islam. They were the examples of honesty, decency, sincerity, trustworthiness, peace and good behavior.

Basically, the objective and purpose of Islam is humanistic, ethical, moral, spiritual and religious. The Shari'a, on the other hand, is always trying to protect and guard individual's integrity and property aright.

Conclusion

From the fore-going discussion, the paper is of the opinion that the Shari'ah legal system or Islam generally has a very important role to play in any crusade against religious crisis, injustice, immorality, illegal killings, insurgency

and brigandage. In fact, Shari'ah remained to be one of the best tools for character modeling which hinges on being God-fearing. It is the Shari'a that reminds and guides a human being on his basic responsibilities as a believer. Such responsibilities comprise commanding the right and forbidding the wrong known as *amr bi al-ma'ruf wa al-nahy an al-munkar*. Fundamentally, the philosophy behind social change is to bring about positive attitudinal change within a given society. The fact is that both society and morality are two sides of the same coin. With this therefore, in any demand for positive change especially in the area of peace and conflict resolution, Shari'ah could play a very gigantic role.

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